

Deliverable D6.2 Training efforts report

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1. Executive Summary

The BY-COVID initiative aimed to speed up infectious disease research, surveillance, and outbreak investigation. It provided access to comprehensive, open, and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data and metadata on SARS-CoV-2, as well as other viruses and infectious diseases. This encompassed data and metadata of the COVID-19 disease across various research fields, including omics, clinical, and epidemiological research, as well as socioeconomic and humanities.

The BY-COVID project was truly interdisciplinary, and depended on a comprehensive understanding of the data provided by project partners. This required adopting common best practices and standards to ensure data mobilisation and FAIRness, and making the best use of project resources and tools. Training, capacity building, and outreach were crucial for establishing common ground among partners and mobilising data both during and after the project.

This deliverable summarises the training efforts carried out throughout the BY-COVID project. During the initial months of the project, we identified the training needs and gaps, as well as the priority target audiences. Subsequently, we developed a roadmap for training, capacity building, and outreach activities. Following this plan, we organised 20 workshops, courses, hackathons, and bridging events with the expertise of BY-COVID partners from the technical Work Packages (WP1-WP6). These events gathered over 2000 participants, twice as many as initially expected. Throughout the project timeline, we also gathered information on project-specific training resources available in national centres, EOSC projects, RIs, and involved partners. Additionally, we made over 70 training materials openly available and FAIR, 40% more than initially anticipated. This deliverable outlines the efforts towards delivering training, capacity building, and outreach activities during BY-COVID, along with their results, impact, and outcomes.

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Enable storage, sharing, access,	1. A research data management practice in European research infrastructures practice that drives discovery, access and reuse of outbreak data and directly links experimental data from	Yes

analysis and processing of research data and other digital research objects from outbreak research	HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EMERGENCY-02 transnational access projects into the COVID-19 Data Portal.	
	2. Openly shared workflows and processing pipelines that integrate transparent quality management and provenance and are openly shared.	Yes
	3. Research infrastructures on-target training so that users can exploit the platform.	Yes
	4. Engagement so that stakeholders (RIs, national centres, policymakers, intergovernmental organisations, funders and end-users) incorporate FAIR and open data in infectious disease guidelines and forward planning.	Yes
Objective 2 Mobilise and expose viral and human infectious disease data from national centres	1. A comprehensive registry of available data with established procedures to collate data governance models, metadata descriptions and access mechanisms in a pandemic scenario.	No
	2. Mechanisms for the initial discovery across data sources based on available metadata at the reference collection.	No
	3. Demonstrated transnational linking of real-world data from national surveillance, healthcare, registries and social science data that allow the assessment of variants to serve the research needs of epidemiology and public health.	No
	4. Demonstrated assessment of emerging SARS-CoV-2 variants against data generated in the ongoing European VACCELERATE clinical trials project to investigate vaccine efficacy.	No
Objective 3 Link FAIR data and metadata on SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19	1. A platform that links normative pathogen genomes and variant representations to research cohorts and mechanistic studies to understand the biomolecular determinants of variant response on patient susceptibility and disease pathways.	No
	2. An open and extensible metadata framework adopted cross-domain that supports comprehensive indexing of the infectious disease resources based on mappings across resources and research domains.	No
	3. A provenance framework for researchers and policy-makers that enables trust in results and provides credit to data submitters, workflow contributors and participant resources.	No
Objective 4 Develop digital tools and data analytics for pandemic and outbreak preparedness,	1. Broad uptake of viral <i>Data Hubs</i> across Europe delivers an order-of-magnitude increase in open viral variant detection and sharing.	Yes
	2. Infrastructure and quality workflows mobilised and shared to produce open, normative variant data that is incorporated into national and regional data systems and decision-making.	Yes

including tracking genomics variations of SARS-CoV-2 and identifying new variants of concern		
<p>Objective 5</p> <p>Contribute to the Horizon Europe European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Partnership and European Health Data Space (EHDS)</p>	<p>1. Guidelines and procedures for FAIR data management and access will be established, building on work of other guideline producing consortia such as the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH), the 1Mio Genomes Initiative (1MG) and the Beyond One Million Genomes project (B1MG).</p> <p>2. Services, software, protocols, guidelines and other research objects that are openly accessible for reuse by the EOSC Association and the community at large as a foundation for European preparedness for infectious diseases, leveraging developments in EOSC-Life, SSHOC, EOSC-Future, EGI-ACE and other EOSC projects.</p> <p>3. Alignment (both policy and implementation routes) will have been achieved between the data governance strategies for routinely collected health data in the EHDS initiative, including the TEHDAS Joint Action and future EHDS Pilot Actions.</p> <p>4. To empower national centres to build capacity and train platform users and data providers (e.g., from life, social or health sciences), and with experts from across partner institutions collaborating to create training materials for the identified gaps, and to exchange experiences and knowledge.</p>	<p>No</p> <p>Yes</p> <p>No</p> <p>Yes</p>

3. Introduction

Work Package 6 of the BY-COVID project aimed to *engage, train and build capacity with national and international stakeholders in support of building an efficient infrastructure for European preparedness for COVID-19 and other infectious diseases*. In Tasks 6.1, 6.2, and 6.3, the focus was on engagement activities at the institutional level. This included engagement with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and the EOSC Association¹, as well as with policy, funders, and regulatory bodies such as the World Health Organization², the European Commission, and the European Health Data Space³. These activities are described separately in D6.1 - Stakeholder engagement report. Task 6.4, on the other hand,

¹ <https://eosc.eu/>

² <https://www.who.int/>

³ https://health.ec.europa.eu/ehealth-digital-health-and-care/european-health-data-space_en

focused on activities at the individual level, specifically on training and capacity-building for researchers, data users and providers, as well as members of the BY-COVID project and related projects such as ISIDORE⁴. However, several of its activities also had an outreach and bridging aspect, contributing to engagement as well, all tasks contributed to dissemination, exploitation and communications of the BY-COVID project. Task 6.4 events and activities were organised to reach a wide community, working with research on infectious and related diseases in health and social sciences. Various interdisciplinary activities were organised to discuss potential future collaborations and the sharing of data.

Task 6.4 coordinated the identification of the project-specific training resources available in national centres, EOSC projects, Research Infrastructures (RIs) and involved partners, and the identification of training needs and gaps. It brought together experts from partner institutions to create training materials, provide training for the identified gaps, exchange experiences and knowledge, and build capacity. All activities were conducted in collaboration with the experts from WP1-6 who provided the training. Task 6.4 also used resources from WP7 to enhance the dissemination and communication of all the events. The events were all announced on the project webpage⁵ and social media⁶.

The BY-COVID project consortium counts over 50 legal entities from 11 Research Infrastructures and 19 European countries. It is a large and genuinely interdisciplinary consortium with partners from various fields, including biomolecular, public health, and clinical and social science research. A deep understanding of the data provided by project partners and their practices was crucial for coordinating efforts to deliver the project's objectives and foster collaborations across the various scientific disciplines of the BY-COVID consortium partners. It was also necessary to mobilise this diverse expertise to provide focused and short training that would promote the usage of the consortium outputs.

The BY-COVID training, capacity building, outreach and bridging events thus aimed to:

- Create capacity and train BY-COVID consortium partners and users to use advanced research tools and methodologies to analyse and manage their data
- Reinforce the project partners' connections
- Disseminate best practices, solutions and methodologies
- Promote the usage of the outputs of the project such as the COVID-19 Data Portal
- Promote adoption of open and FAIR principles

⁴ <https://isidore-project.eu/>

⁵ <https://by-covid.org/events>

⁶ https://x.com/BYCOVID_eu

3.1 Methodology

As a start, we identified the best ways to assess the training needs and gaps together with the BY-COVID community. For that, we organised a dedicated workshop where all BY-COVID Research Infrastructures were invited to present their strategies to identify training needs, and which concluded with a round of discussions. The main strategies described by the workshop participants used to assess training needs were: surveys, direct discussions and workshops. We have decided that informal individual discussions across BY-COVID WPs (WP1-WP6) would lead to a more pragmatic and fast way to identify immediate training needs as well as any other needs that would appear along the lifespan of the project. We decided as well that surveying communities, e.g. sending a small set of questions, would be a secondary option, only used in very special cases. For instance, through a short survey, we inquired about the training needs from the National coordinators group, which was mainly composed of COVID-19 data providers (those producing the data such as hospitals and laboratories) and brokers (those cleaning, formatting, curating the data previous to the submission to the data platforms) from the life sciences domain (policy, clinical and researchers). However, that survey only gathered 5 answers and only one training-related request.

3.1.1 Audiences prioritised

In order to maximise and optimise the training efforts of the BY-COVID project, during that initial workshop, and in following meetings with the WP6 members, we identified the target and priority audiences to whom we would address the BY-COVID training:

1. BY-COVID developers working in the WPs 1-5, with the objective to facilitate their collaborations and their contributions to the outputs of the project,
2. BY-COVID partners contributing to WPs 1-8 in any way, with the objective to develop a common language across partners RI and institutions, increase and facilitate the interactions of the BY-COVID members,
3. Data providers and data brokers of SARS-CoV-2 and other infectious agents data, with the objective of increasing the number of institutions mobilising and making infectious disease-related data available,
4. Consumers of the data mobilised in BY-COVID as well as of the workflows, tools and the Infectious Disease Toolkit⁷ (IDTk) produced in the BY-COVID project, with the objective to teach the usage of the BY-COVID products and outputs, facilitate their discovery and disseminate information about them.

Throughout the project, these audiences became better defined, concrete and specific. For instance, as the sibling project ISIDORE⁸ (Integrated Services for Infections Disease Outbreak Research) progressed, their data producers became our main priority in category 4, and some of the events we have organised - for instance, the workshop “Unlocking the

⁷ <https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/>

⁸ <https://isidore-project.eu/>

power of metadata” - were created with ISIDORE’s requirements in mind, but as well for the whole BY-COVID community (categories 1-4 above).

3.1.2 Topics of training, capacity building, outreach and bridging events

Some topics identified in the early stages of the project included the data available in the Pathogen Portal⁹, the use of BEACON¹⁰ for data discovery, the use of metadata standards, and other technical aspects of data management, as well as training on the General Data Protection Regulation¹¹ (GDPR) and data privacy issues. Other topics were inserted along the way such as training to lower the barrier for data deposition for sequence data providers who have no expertise/support available by their organisation.

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Description of the events

During the lifespan of the BY-COVID project, we organised 20 workshops, courses, hackathons, and bridging events with the expertise of BY-COVID partners from WP1-WP5, which are summarised in Figure 1. Along the project, we have kept track of these events, KPI (Key Performance Indicator), training materials collected, and any useful information in a single common **Training Inventory**¹² document.

4.1.1 Virtual CABANA Workshops: Innovative methods for viral detection and discovery in genomic and metagenomic data

Type of event: Courses

Aim(s) of the event: Introduce the **COVID-19 Data Portal**¹³, what data types are included, provide a tour, demonstrate features and demonstrate searching and browsing of data

Target audience: Researchers

Attendance: 30 participants in each of the two course instances

WPs involved: WP1

Short description: The COVID-19 Data Portal was presented as part of a CABANA¹⁴ (Capacity building for bioinformatics in Latin America) workshop, which overall covered retrieval, analysis and data sharing. The session included presentations and exercises which got users to think about how to query/search, retrieve data, access and use available

⁹ <https://www.pathogensportal.org/>

¹⁰ <https://beacon-project.io/>

¹¹ <https://gdpr-info.eu/>

¹² BY-COVID [Training Inventory](#)

¹³ <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/>

¹⁴ <https://www.cabana.online/index>

tools in the COVID-19 Data Portal, such as the CoVEO¹⁵ explorer with SARS-CoV-2 variant reports, and the SARS-CoV-2 phylogeny tree¹⁶.

Figure 1: Overview and timeline of the BY-COVID training events

4.1.2 The Pathogens Portal: A gateway to vast biomolecular data for pathogen research

Type of event: Webinar

Aim(s) of the event: Introduce the Pathogens Portal, what data types are included, provide a tour and demonstrate searching and browsing of data

Target audience: Researchers, public health officials, institutes, life science companies

Attendance: 120 attendees

WPs involved: WP1

Short description: The ENA and EMBL-EBI training team organised a webinar, that was part of a series of webinars around Exploring microbial ecosystems. The webinar focused on providing users more information about the **Pathogens Portal**¹⁷, whilst providing an on-demand webinar available for users to see after the actual recording. The webinar was suitable for anyone interested in exploring pathogens and microbial ecosystems and didn't

¹⁵ <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/coveo>

¹⁶ <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/phylogeny-tree>

¹⁷ <https://www.pathogensportal.org/>

require any prior knowledge of bioinformatics. By the end of the webinar, users would be able to identify the criteria for selecting pathogens to be included in the Pathogens Portal, describe key features of the portal, including the various sections, and demonstrate basic navigation and search functions.

4.1.3 BY-COVID hackathons to onboard resources to the COVID-19 data portal - WP3 Discoverability hackathons

Type of event: Hackathons

Aim(s) of the event: Guide how to provide metadata for making content of a data resource discoverable through the COVID-19 Data Portal, and how to register a resource in FAIRsharing¹⁸

Target audience: Technical representatives of public data resources with content related to COVID-19 or the larger pandemic preparedness context.

Attendance: 64 participants in total for both hackathons

WPs involved: WP3, WP6

Short description: The **COVID-19 Data Portal**¹⁹ is a central, high level entry point of COVID-19 related knowledge across a broad range of domains, from molecular biology to clinical data and socioeconomic data, to connect information across the EOSC ecosystem as well as with international resources. Two hackathons were organised in 2022 and 2023. The first one focussed on guiding how data producers can submit their metadata in the Portal and thus increase the visibility and discoverability of their data, how to register resources in FAIRsharing, and on structuring the content of the Portal. The second one provided a quick overview of the principles and continued with concrete examples from social sciences and humanities and cohort data, and on how to provide metadata in the required format.

4.1.4 Galaxy Training Network course and Smörgåsbords

Type of event: Several training modules

Aim(s) of the event: Analyse SARS-CoV-2 data and create FAIR workflows

Target audience: Researchers

Attendance: 1069 participants in total all BY-COVID modules

WPs involved: WP4

Short description: Erasmus MC and the Galaxy Training Network²⁰ organised one course on SARS-CoV-2 data analysis and monitoring with Galaxy²¹ and two Galaxy Smörgåsbord training events in 2022 and 2023. The Smörgåsbord, global and very large events, featured lectures from experts, hands-on tutorials, and demos which leveraged Galaxy as a convenient, web-accessible service on which to conduct the training. The compute access

¹⁸ <https://fairsharing.org/>

¹⁹ <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/>

²⁰ <https://training.galaxyproject.org>

²¹ <https://usegalaxy-eu.github.io/event/2021-09-15-sars-cov-2-training/>

provided by Galaxy ensured access for those in LMICs, enabling us to reach 3k and 3.3k registrations each year respectively across 5 modules each year. In the Smörgåsbord 2022²², we have incorporated and updated the **SARS-CoV-2 Data Analysis** module which includes an Introduction to Galaxy and genomics based analysis (removal of human reads from SARS-CoV-2, SARS-CoV-2 data analysis on public datasets, sequencing automation and monitoring), visualisation and data export, unicycler assembly of SARS-CoV-2 genome and pandemics research using mass spectrometry. For the 2023²³ edition, we have reused an updated version of the 2022 SARS-CoV-2 Data Analysis module and included a new module on the **RO-Crate** training material²⁴ instructing users on how to ensure their workflows are completely FAIR.

4.1.5 BEACON workshop - How to make sensitive data discoverable

Type of event: Course

Aim(s) of the event: Provide knowledge and hands-on practice about the discoverability of sensitive genomics and clinical data without compromising privacy or ownership.

Target audience: Clinicians, researchers, programmers, bioinformaticians

Attendance: 78 participants

WPs involved: WP2, WP6

Short description: One of the main bottlenecks in human data research is the lack of tools for the secure and federated data discovery of such data. The European Genome-phenome Archive²⁵ (EGA) in collaboration with ELIXIR and the Global Alliance in Health and Genomics²⁶ (GA4GH) has developed the **Beacon**²⁷ project to tackle this challenge. This hands-on training session, targeted at the BY-COVID partners, aimed to introduce them to the application of Beacon to their datasets. This course was divided in two sessions: 1) an introduction and operational principles of Beacon, oriented towards clinicians & researchers working with human data (mutations, variants, Covid-19 patients etc), genomics data (VCF files) and/or associated phenoclinic metadata, and 2) the implementation and deployment of Beacon, oriented towards software developers & bioinformaticians.

4.1.6 Unlocking the Power of Metadata

Type of event: Bridging event, workshop

Aim(s) of the event: Create a common ground on **metadata** and their importance for **FAIR** knowledge systems to accelerate science with data-driven approaches

Target audience: Researchers, data analysts and anyone interested in better understanding what metadata is and its importance

²² Smörgåsbord 2022 Tapas Edition: <https://gallantries.github.io/video-library/events/smorgasbord2/tapas.html>

²³ Galaxy Smörgåsbord 2023 Edition: <https://gallantries.github.io/video-library/events/smorgasbord3/>

²⁴ <https://gxy.io/GTN:N00052>

²⁵ <https://ega-archive.org>

²⁶ <https://www.ga4gh.org>

²⁷ <https://beacon-project.io/>

Attendance: 85 participants

WPs involved: WP1-WP6

Short description: In this short but practical workshop²⁸, all members of the BY-COVID and sibling partner initiatives were invited to discover the importance and benefits of metadata. It included a basic introduction to data, metadata, vocabularies, taxonomies, and ontologies and several illustrations of data and metadata from, for instance, ISIDORe, public health data, Schema.org, the COVID-19 Portal, and FAIRsharing and standards. For the hands-on session, the participants discovered how to create their own DCAT metadata records from the metadata of their projects.

4.1.7 BY-COVID Spring 2023 Use Cases Workshop: Integration of socioeconomic data in observational studies on vaccine effectiveness.

Type of event: Bridging event

Aim(s) of the event: Contributing to the integration of socioeconomic data in the Baseline Use Case, and identifying the Dutch-Belgian landscape

Target audience: BY-COVID members and non-members; Researchers and data holders, mainly from the social sciences

Attendance: 23 participants

WPs involved: WP3, WP5, WP6

Short description: This workshop was organised in the context of, and in contribution to, the BY-COVID **Baseline Use Case** (WP5), with the support of WP6. The Baseline Use Case aimed to provide a structured process for leveraging observational real-world data sources to respond to policy-relevant questions. The first research question concerned the real-world effectiveness of SARS-CoV-2 vaccination in populations spanning national borders. The workshop took place face-to-face in The Hague, the Netherlands at the premises of NWO (the Dutch Research Council) on April 26th 2023 and was co-organised by CESSDA/KNAW-DANS, Sciensano, and IACS. The main aims of the workshop were:

- To promote further development of the BY-COVID Baseline Use Case, and stimulate community discussion around it;
- To highlight relevant initiatives and practices in the Dutch and Belgian landscape;
- To discuss issues surrounding socioeconomic data requirements, mobilisation, and protection in different national contexts in the form of breakout sessions;
- To highlight how real-world vaccine effectiveness can be estimated in a causal framework by combining administrative, health and care data with data on socioeconomic factors.

The results of the workshop were compiled into a Workshop Report, which was published on Zenodo²⁹ for training and outreach purposes. The workshop contributed to the follow-up workshop described below.

²⁸ Unlocking the Power of Metadata

²⁹ <https://zenodo.org/records/8234104>

4.1.8 BY-COVID Spring 2024 Baseline Use Case Workshop: Integration of individual-level socioeconomic data for infectious diseases research and prevention in Europe.

Type of event: Bridging event

Aim(s) of the event: Building on the above Spring 2023 workshop by practically integrating socioeconomic data in the Baseline Use-case at the European level; contributing to the summary report.

Target audience: BY-COVID members and non-members, researchers and data holders, mainly from the social sciences

Attendance: 13 participants

WPs involved: WP3, WP5, WP6

Short description: This workshop built on the Spring 23 workshop above, by aiming to identify practical solutions for integrating socioeconomic data in the **Baseline Use Case** on the European Level. The workshop took place online on June 6th, and featured presentations on the latest progress on the BY-COVID Baseline Use Case, including its associated methodology and workflow, as well as reports from the data providers outlining progress and challenges. The workshop presentations were recorded, and will be made available together with slides and other materials on Zenodo before the end of the project for training and outreach purposes. The workshop also directly contributes to a report³⁰ on the integration of socioeconomic data in the Baseline Use Case, which aims to describe how this work was carried out.

4.1.9 BY-COVID-GDPR Workshop

Type of event: Engagement and training workshop

Aim(s) of the event: Engagement across disciplines and knowledge exchange with regards to GDPR limitations and challenges.

Target audience: researchers, data professionals, project managers.

Attendance: 25 participants

WPs involved: WP2, WP6

Short description: This workshop took place during the 5th BY-COVID consortium meeting on 10 October 2023 in Barcelona. It focused on **data management compliance with GDPR**, challenges, and opportunities across disciplines. It included examples and participation from the life, health, and social sciences members attending the consortium meeting. It was also set up to identify the priority topics that needed to be treated in the BY-COVID Fest event (see below).

³⁰ [Integration socio-economic data: report](#)

4.1.10 Research Data Management Training - Preparing to manage your data across disciplines

Type of event: Courses

Aim(s) of the event: To train the participants on RDM practices and tools by discussing use cases and challenges across disciplines.

Target audience: researchers, data professionals, project managers.

Attendance: 108 attendees in total in the three modules

WPs involved: WP2, WP6

Short description: The courses³¹ were designed and delivered with the collaboration of partners representing the life, social and health sciences. BY-COVID partners showcased and provided training and guidance on **Research Data Management** (RDM) practices, tools, use cases and challenges when managing research data. The three courses were delivered in the form of webinars, also allowing space for questions and interaction, as follows:

- 17 October 2023: Data management in social sciences and humanities with **DMEG**³²
- 22 November 2023: Data management in life sciences with **RDMkit**³³
- 12 December 2023: Use cases, challenges and issues in data management

4.1.11 BY-COVID Fest

Type of event: Training, capacity building and bridging event, in-person.

Aim(s) of the event: Empower data users and producers to become confident in submitting or using sensitive data, express their questions and issues to professionals in their institutions, and find solutions for their sensitive data issues.

Target audience: Researchers, data producers, BY-COVID partners, data protection officers, data professionals, project managers.

Attendance: 47 participants

WPs involved: WP1-WP6

Short description: The BY-COVID Fest took place on 23-25 January 2024 in Athens as a bridging event of two streams. The training stream on **Data sharing and reuse under GDPR** brought together experts of different backgrounds and across disciplines, featuring lectures, real-life use cases and demos. Lively discussions and interactive sessions allowed participants to discuss, learn, and exchange experiences on different points of view, issues, challenges, and solutions across disciplines relevant to infectious diseases. Participants were expected to leave the event with improved confidence in publishing or using sensitive data, expressing their questions and concerns to data protection experts, and implementing effective solutions to ensure data integrity and security. The outcomes of the workshop were documented in a Workshop Report, which was subsequently published on Zenodo³⁴.

³¹ RDM courses: <https://by-covid.org/events/research-data-management-training/>

³² <https://dmeg.cessda.eu/>

³³ <https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>

³⁴ BY-COVID Fest, GDPR report: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11220597>

4.1.12 Using containers as SPEs in federated research architectures for health data reuse

Type of event: Workshop

Aim(s) of the event: Raise awareness of the utility of employing containers, as **Secure Processing Environments**, when distributing **sensitive health data**, troubleshooting the deployment of containers.

Target audience: Researchers producing and/or working with sensitive data and personnel with a more technical background who actively support these researchers.

Attendance: 47 participants

WPs involved: WP5, WP6

Short description: **Containers**, built using software like Docker, can package code executing statistical analyses with the required dependencies and provide a fixed **Secured Processing Environment** (SPE). Distributing code to perform statistical analyses reusing sensitive health data in a federated research network can thus benefit from containers, which ensure the reproducibility of analyses in federated analysis architectures. This workshop included participants from the BY-COVID WP5 **Baseline Use Case**, any BY-COVID partner or anyone interested in the topic. It was designed to raise participants' awareness of the utility of employing containers when distributing sensitive health data and cultivate a sense of trust and confidence in using containers in this context. This workshop was also intended to explore and identify the organisational requirements and potential barriers to implementing containers and provide practical solutions to the deployment of containers for statistical analysis in a federated research network.

4.1.13 Euro-BioImaging's Guide to FAIR Bioimage Data

Type of event: Two online Workshops in 2023 and 2024

Aim(s) of the event: Introduction to the FAIR principles and relevant repositories in the context of bioimaging data, FAIR data management

Target audience: Researchers working with imaging data across all scales of bioimaging (from molecules to humans) and individuals who support them (e.g. data analysts, data stewards, technical personnel), everyone interested in FAIR principles, BY-COVID partners

Attendance: 123 participants

WPs involved: WP2

Short description: In these interactive online workshops participants were introduced to the **FAIR principles**³⁵ in the context of **bioimaging data** and were provided simple yet effective steps for a smooth start to a FAIR journey. The course covered the benefits of FAIR data for molecular, cellular as well as pre-clinical imaging and best practices for data management including an advanced lecture on cloud-compatible next-generation file formats for image data. Featuring invited speakers from bioimaging repositories, a significant portion of the workshop was dedicated to the topic of data sharing and

³⁵ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

deposition. Additionally, participants had the chance to directly test and apply their freshly gained knowledge through practical tasks in interactive breakout sessions.

4.1.14 BY-COVID and EATRIS workshop on long-COVID-19

Type of event: Bridging event

Aim(s) of the event: To bring together the **Long Covid network** of EATRIS and BY-COVID project members to exchange knowledge and experiences and explore synergies for further work.

Target audience: Key members of the EATRIS Long Covid network representative WP members from across the BY-COVID project.

Attendance: Attendance was by invitation only, with 16 participants attending in person and two attending remotely.

WPs involved: WP1-7

Short description: This event brought together key members of the **EATRIS³⁶ Long Covid** network with key representatives from across the BY-COVID work packages to share experiences and knowledge in their respective projects to date and then identify key challenges and opportunities going forward. The EATRIS Long Covid network has recently developed and submitted a COST action to further strengthen and expand their existing efforts in creating a network for researchers focused on the topic of Long Covid. This network includes the need for data focused individuals, including the capture of appropriate data (including clinical, biological and socioeconomic), researchers with experience of AI and modelling, plus engagement with industry. On day 1 both groups presented their work to date, including challenges faced and achievements so far, including an overview of the IDTK for the Long Covid network. Day 2 then focused on a discussion of the COST action proposal and joint challenges arising from day 1. A number of key links between work undertaken within BY-COVID and the COST action work were noted, and these will be further explored and highlighted to both strengthen the COST action proposal and further the sustainability of work undertaken through the BY-COVID project. Additionally some further routes to enable members of the groups to work together were explored, including potential funding routes. The potential of the addition of a Long Covid data focused section to the IDTK is also being explored.

4.1.15 Maturity Model for Pathogen Data Platforms

Type of event: Workshop

Aim(s) of the event: Showcase the usage of the **Maturity Model** for **Pathogen Data Platforms**

Target audience: Platform managers and those involved in platform development such as bioinformaticians, ITs, and legal services.

Attendance: 17 participants

WPs involved: WP4, WP6

³⁶ <https://eatris.eu>

Short description: **Maturity models** are a useful tool to support data platform management when assessing current maturity and development lifecycle gaps. The Pathogen Data Platform maturity model³⁷ specifically targets data platforms that host pathogens and associated, contextually sensitive, personal metadata. This model was developed within ELIXIR-CONVERGE³⁸ and tested in a pilot run within BY-COVID. During this highly interactive workshop, practical illustrations were presented of how to understand and score the various indicators of the maturity model, with examples focusing on SARS-CoV-2, bacterial, and wastewater data. We also discussed the importance of ensuring FAIRness of platforms by design and how maturity models can support this.

4.2 Training materials

4.1.1 The collections

Training materials were created for most of the events listed in the previous session of this deliverable, and they are openly available as a collection on the Resources page of the BY-COVID website³⁹. These materials were also connected either directly to the IDTK Training⁴⁰ resources page or, whenever appropriate, to the pages where the topic was directly related to the training material. This was the case, for instance, for the Pathogen characterisation⁴¹ page.

Training materials created in BY-COVID by members of partners organisation:

Members of the Galaxy Training Network (GTN) who were part of the BY-COVID project have also created new tutorials to explain and demonstrate in detail how to perform different types of analyses of infectious disease data with the Galaxy analysis environment. These materials are available on the dedicated BY-COVID GTN⁴² page, and included:

- GTN:T00316⁴³ - a tutorial detailing a complete analysis flow from sequencing data obtained from the COVID-19 Data Portal through mutation calling and viral consensus genome construction to SARS-CoV-2 lineage/clade assignment with pangolin and/or nextclade,
- GTN:T00236⁴⁴ - a tutorial showing how to remove traces of human genomic data from sequenced SARS-CoV-2 data,

³⁷Pathogen Data Platform maturity model: <https://elixir-europe.github.io/pdp-maturity-model/>

³⁸<https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/how-funded/eu-projects/converge>

³⁹<https://by-covid.org/resources>

⁴⁰<https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/training-resources-list/>

⁴¹<https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/data-description/pathogen-characterisation>

⁴²<https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/hall-of-fame/by-covid/>

⁴³<https://gxy.io/GTN:T00316>

⁴⁴<https://gxy.io/GTN:T00236>

- GTN:T00347⁴⁵ - a tutorial on pox virus genome analysis from tiled-amplicon sequencing data,
- GTN:T00308⁴⁶ - a tutorial on Avian influenza genome analysis from per-segment sequencing data,
- GTN:T00437⁴⁷ - a tutorial detailing contrast analysis of transcriptome data from COVID-19 patients and healthy controls. It showcases visualisation of results on the MINERVA Platform COVID-19 Disease Map,
- GTN:S00064⁴⁸ and GTN:T00159⁴⁹ - slides and tutorial to explain how to use the tool to upload data from the Galaxy analysis environment to the COVID-19 Data Portal.

FAIRsharing is a widely adopted, curated, informative and educational resource on standards related to repositories and policies across all disciplines. FAIRsharing provides a vast collection of 99 resources potentially relevant to COVID-19 research. For the BY-COVID project, a FAIRsharing BY-COVID Collection⁵⁰ was created with the ultimate scope of 'pushing' the descriptions of the data sources and their standards into the OpenAIRE Research Graph, enabling it to be part of the EOSC ecosystem. Also, during the BY-COVID project, several FAIRsharing training materials⁵¹ were developed to promote and facilitate the use of FAIRsharing among BY-COVID partners.

Collections of training materials from Research Infrastructures in BY-COVID

In the first year of the BY-COVID project, we have compiled a "collection of collections" of training materials (Table 1) from the Research Infrastructures represented in BY-COVID and from other institutions. These collections bring together educational resources that the BY-COVID partners can utilise for self-learning. They also highlight topics that have already been covered by these Research Infrastructures, which are directly relevant to BY-COVID but may not require inclusion in the BY-COVID training events. Additionally, they help identify training gaps that must be addressed in the BY-COVID training events, with some adjustments to cater to the project's audience and objectives.

⁴⁵ <https://gxy.io/GTN:T00347>

⁴⁶ <https://gxy.io/GTN:T00308>

⁴⁷ <https://gxy.io/GTN:T00437>

⁴⁸ <https://gxy.io/GTN:S00064>

⁴⁹ <https://gxy.io/GTN:T00159>

⁵⁰ <https://fairsharing.org/3773>

⁵¹ <https://fairsharing.org/educational>

Table 1. Collections of training materials from BY-COVID Research Infrastructures and other initiatives and institutions

Title	Description
DARIAH-Campus ⁵²	For arts and humanities scholars working in computational methods. It supports digital research as well as the teaching of digital research methods.
EOSC Synergy Online Training Handbook ⁵³	A practical course and handbook with guidelines and templates for designing, creating and delivering online training, with a focus on EOSC, FAIR and open science.
EOSC-Life ⁵⁴	Building a digital space for the Life Sciences
EOSC-Pillar Training and Support ⁵⁵	A collection of online searchable resources for Data Stewardship and Research Data Management support
FAIR Cookbook ⁵⁶	The ELIXIR FAIR Cookbook is an online resource for the Life Sciences with recipes that help you to make and keep data FAIR
FAIRsharing Educational ⁵⁷	Educational material by the FAIRsharing Team and RDA/EOSC FAIRsharing Community Champions, covering content and functionalities on standards, databases and policies.
Galaxy Training Material ⁵⁸	Collection of >300 tutorials developed and maintained by the worldwide Galaxy community
Health Information Training catalogue - PHIRI ⁵⁹	For capacity building activities on COVID-19, population health and health information organised by PHIRI and other International Health Information Organizations and Institutions
RDMkit ⁶⁰	The ELIXIR online guide contains good data management practices applicable to research projects from the beginning to the end.
SSHOC Training Discovery Toolkit ⁶¹	Training catalogue with courses, training materials, collections and workflows in social sciences and humanities
TeSS - ELIXIR's Training Portal ⁶²	Training catalogue with courses, training materials, collections and workflows in life sciences

⁵² <https://campus.dariah.eu>

⁵³ <https://moodle.learn.eosc-synergy.eu/course/view.php?id=15§ion=10#tabs-tree-start>

⁵⁴ <https://www.eosc-life.eu/services/training/>

⁵⁵ <https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org/group/eoscpillartrainingandsupport/home>

⁵⁶ <https://faircookbook.elixir-europe.org/>

⁵⁷ <https://fairsharing.org/educational>

⁵⁸ <https://training.galaxyproject.org/>

⁵⁹ <https://www.healthinformationportal.eu/activities/catalogue>

⁶⁰ <https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org>

⁶¹ https://training-toolkit.sshopencloud.eu/entities?search=&f%5B0%5D=content_type%3Asource

⁶² <https://tess.elixir-europe.org>

4.1.2 FAIRification process

Training materials include any digital object used in a training context (e.g., slide presentations, videos, exercises, datasets, etc.). As with any digital object, they can be openly accessible and FAIRified to be more findable and reusable⁶³. These principles are the basis of the BY-COVID project and have also become a goal for the WP6 members. Most of the training materials of the BY-COVID project have been made openly available (they are findable in the BY-COVID project Resource page and on project's Zenodo community), and other steps for their FAIRification were started. For instance, ensuring data and materials sharing by linking from the BY-COVID website to IDTk. Some of the steps still remaining include inserting the appropriate metadata describing the materials so repositories such as ELIXIR TeSS or CESSDA training catalogue can scrape them, as well as providing a licence and a unique PID. The objective is to finish the complete FAIRification process, as per the ELIXIR FAIR handbook⁶⁴, by the end of the project (Sep 2024).

5. Results

During the project's initial months, the training needs and gaps were analysed, and the priority target audiences for the training activities were determined. Subsequently, a roadmap outlining the strategies for conducting training, capacity building, and outreach activities was developed.

Following the initial set plan, which evolved along with the project's progress, 20 workshops, courses, hackathons, and bridging events were successfully organised and delivered. These events were made possible through the collaboration and expertise of BY-COVID partners from WP1-WP5. These events attracted participation from over 2000 individuals, which was double the number initially anticipated.

Throughout the project timeline, information on project-specific training resources available in national centres, EOSC projects, research infrastructures (RIs), and among the partners were gathered, as well as awareness of the project partners to scout for similar resources. It's important to note that more than 70 openly accessible training materials were created, exceeding the initial target by 40%. Making materials as FAIR as possible is the remaining goal of this task, which should be accomplished until the end of the project.

6. Impact

⁶³ Ten simple rules for making training materials FAIR:

<https://journals.plos.org/ploscompbiol/article?id=10.1371/journal.pcbi.1007854>

⁶⁴ <https://elixir-europe-training.github.io/ELIXIR-TrP-FAIR-training-handbook/>

Measuring the impact of training activities is crucial to understanding their effectiveness. There are several approaches to carrying out this measurement, such as collecting trainees' reactions through surveys or feedback forms and assessing learning through tests or exams. However, due to the diverse backgrounds of partners involved, a lighter approach to measure the impact of training through informal feedback was chosen, allowing participants to share their thoughts and experiences. For example, at the BY-COVID Fest, which brought together various BY-COVID members and experts, very positive written and oral feedback from the participants was received along with testimonials. Two illustrations of these testimonials are: "Thank you very much for the great opportunity to participate in the interesting meeting in Athens. I'm looking forward to continue the collaboration and the opportunity of future projects.", and "My colleague and I found the talks incredibly interesting and valuable".

Sixty-four people attended the hackathons to onboard resources to the COVID-19 data portal (WP3 Discoverability hackathons); it is expected that at least 1/3 of those used the metadata model developed in WP3 to support the three-tiered discoverability concept in the COVID-19 Data Portal. Thanks to the RDM events, BY-COVID and sibling project partners, from national and international research infrastructures, have now improved their foundational data management skills and have a better understanding of the challenges faced when collecting and working with sensitive health data.

Although formal measurement or monitoring of the impact of the BY-COVID training events did not take place, it can be inferred that they had a positive effect. The dissemination of the training events reached a diverse audience, both within and outside of the project consortium, expanding its reach. It can also be inferred that the training events positively impacted the progress of the work delivered by the project partners, leading to a better understanding of the partners' topics and environments. Ultimately, this will enable the mobilisation of new data, connections, exposure, use, and analysis of existing data, as well as the sharing of it as openly as possible.

7. Conclusions and next steps

The BY-COVID project was established with specific objectives to improve the ability to gather data for its consortium partners and users through training and capacity-building activities reported in this deliverable. These objectives focused on providing individuals with the skills to use advanced research tools and methodologies for data analysis and management, especially for COVID-19 and future pandemic data.

The training events actively promoted the direct products of BY-COVID (e.g. COVID-19 Data Portal and IDTk) and disseminated best practices, solutions, and methodologies developed within the consortium to a broader audience. These activities also advocated for adopting

open and FAIR data principles to maintain the integrity and utility of scientific data during a global health crisis.

An unplanned but crucial objective of the BY-COVID project was to strengthen the network among project partners. Training activities facilitated a collaborative environment where partners supported each other and shared valuable insights and knowledge. Interdisciplinarity evolved as an asset, and the collaborations initiated in this project will undoubtedly continue in future projects. The training materials created during the project's lifespan will continue to be findable and reusable – two legacies of this collective effort.

The activities reported in this deliverable contributed to the project's success in supporting the response to COVID-19 and preparing for future pandemic challenges.

8. Deviations from the Description of Action

No deviations from the description of action are reported.

9. References

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